

A new ranking approach for E-commerce websites based on fuzzy TOPSIS algorithm

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ABSTRACT

With the gigantic growth of the E-commerce market, E-commerce websites are becoming more and more numerous. Customers of E-commerce websites are spoiled for choice and have encountered several problems in choosing not only the right products but also the E-commerce website from which they want to purchase the desired products. E-commerce websites ranking is recognized as a complex multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) problem. In practice, clients of E-commerce websites generally have difficulty expressing their judgments in precise numbers because the criteria are sometimes imprecise and sometimes uncertain and ambiguous. In this context, we propose to use fuzzy logic to allow clients to express their ratings in natural language and propose an approach based fuzzy technique for order preference by similarity to the ideal solution (TOPSIS) for E-commerce websites ranking. A numerical experimentation was conducted for validate the effectiveness of the proposed approach.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) is an operations research sub-discipline that allows for the explicit assessment of several conflicting criteria in decision-making. It leads to better considered, justifiable, explainable and transparent decisions, because it allows to deal simultaneously and in a transparent way of often contradictory and contradictory points of view [1]. Structuring a complex problem well and considering multiple criteria explicitly leads to more informed and better decisions. The actual application of multicriteria decision making requires the processing of imprecise, uncertain, and qualitative or fuzzy data. An efficient way to model uncertainty and imprecision is to use fuzzy logic and more specifically fuzzy set theory. Fuzzy sets provide the flexibility to represent and manage uncertainty and imprecision resulting from a lack of knowledge or ill-defined information [2]. Ranking E-commerce websites and providing customers with the best fit for them automatically comes down to solving an MCDM problem (several alternatives with several common criteria). The ranking of E-commerce websites is considered as a complex MCDM problem. Several works such as [3] have addressed this problem by relying on MCDM methods.

On another side, it is sometimes difficult to define with precision the criteria of quality of service because the qualities of the services related to a set of E-commerce websites are imprecise and sometimes uncertain and ambiguous, therefore, it is therefore preferable that quality of service (QoS) properties are in linguistic terms (bad, average good, and excellent). This presentation makes it easier for customers and experts to evaluate different alternatives. Fuzzy logic comes to enable this presentation as it supports the representation

of imprecise QoS constraints. In this study, we present a new ranking approach for E-commerce websites based on fuzzy technique for order preference by similarity to the ideal solution (TOPSIS) algorithm. More precisely, we focus on the fuzzy TOPSIS method to assess and rank E-commerce websites.

This paper is organized as follows: section 2 presents some related work. Section 3 describes web sites E-commerce criteria evaluation. In the sections 4 and 5 we present successively membership function and fuzzy TOPSIS method. In section 6, we present our proposed approach. Before concluding we detail in section 7, a numerical illustration with the obtained experimentation results. Finally, section 9 presents a conclusion and future directions of this work.

2. RELATED WORK

Awasthi *et al.* [4], tackled the problem of environmental performance of suppliers, to resolve it they propose an evaluation using an approach based on fuzzy multi-criteria. The mentioned solution composed by three steps: (i) involves the identification of criteria for assessing environmental performance of suppliers; (ii) the experts evaluate each of the selected criteria using linguistic assessments then evaluate the different alternatives according to each criterion evaluated previously; (iii) through fuzzy TOPSIS method they combine the resulted alternatives to generate an overall performance score, then the authors select the best alternative with the highest score.

Order to achieve the high level of durable security in web applications, the authors propose the fuzzy analytic hierarchy process (AHP) method to assess the effectiveness of overall durable security and its characteristics [5]. Bire *et al.* [6] presented research that aims to create a decision support system for selecting tourist attractions using the fuzzy AHP method. Sahu *et al.* [7] proposed a method based on the two fuzzy MCDM method AHP and TOPSIS to ensure the sustainability of web applications.

Pattnaik *et al.* [8] proposed a method of selection of the best insurance company for buy a term plan online. They opted for the fuzzy TOPSIS method to make the selection. In their experiments, they test their approach for twelve (alternative) companies characterized by ten criteria, each of which is expressed in linguistic terms (very low, low, medium, high, and very high).

Kumar *et al.* in [9] focussed on the security and usability of web applications to satisfy the end user. They propose a fuzzy AHP-TOPSIS based method to assess the usability and security of the web application and also identify the attribute with the highest priority in building the usable security of the web application. Fuzzy AHP is used to calculate the weights of each criterion while fuzzy TOPSIS is used to assigning scores.

Zhao and Bose [10] confirmed that it is possible to apply MCDM methods with fuzzy logic in order to deal with imprecision in decision-making problems. The authors describe the famous methods MCDM such as fuzzy AHP, fuzzy analytic network process (ANP), fuzzy TOPSIS, fuzzy preference ranking organization method for enrichment evaluation (PROMETHEE), and combined fuzzy MCDM methods. The authors focus on the application of these methods in the field of energy. Rouyendegh *et al.* [11] proposed a new framework which combine two methods analytic hierarchy process (AHP) and fuzzy TOPSIS technique. The authors invent this solution to asses and evaluate E-commerce web site (EWS) performance. The proposed idea composed by five steps. In their case study, they test the model with three E-commerce websites, each of which is characterized by four criteria which are: system quality, information quality, service quality, and attractiveness.

3. E-COMMERCE WEBSITES CRITERIA EVALUATION

Sulova [12] presented two basic types for evaluating E-commerce websites. The functionality of E-commerce website and the E-commerce website as a marketing tool. The first family includes several criteria such as structure and design of the catalog of products or services, registration system and data transfer security while the second family presents a lot of criteria such as site content, graphic design of the website, and organization and navigation of the site.

Merwe and Bekker [13] proposed a framework for evaluating E-commerce websites. It consists of five categories of criteria that serve as an evaluation framework covering all relevant aspects of the E-commerce website. These categories of criteria are; Interface: it contains graphic design principles, graphic and multimedia, style and text and flexibility and computability. Navigation: it contains logical structure, ease to use, search engine, and navigational necessities. Content: it contains product/service-related information, company and contact information, information quality, and interactivity. Reliability: it contains stored consumer profile, order process, after-order to order receipt, and consumerservice. Technical: it contains speed, security, software and dataset and system design.

Zo and Ramamurthy [14] proposed a consumer selection model of websites in a business to consumer (B2C) environment the in which the author offers three of the criteria for choosing B2C E-commerce websites. The author classify factors for choosing B2C E-commerce web sites in three major categories: products

characteristics, website characteristics and user (consumer) characteristics. Huizingh in [15], the author distinguishes between the content and the design of an E-commerce website, content includes: information content, since the main purpose of the site is to provide commercial information on both the company and the product, as well as other information. Transactional content including ordering and tendering, the size of which is directly related to the size of the website.

As for website design, it includes navigation tree, hyperlinks and search functions. Liang *et al.* [16] described another criteria for E-commerce website evaluation. It details four criteria efficiency, system availability, fulfilment, and privacy. Each one is described by a set of information. For example system availability criterion has got four sub-criteria which are: the website is always available; the website launches and runs immediately; the website does not crash; pages in this website do not freeze after the entry of order information.

4. MEMBERSHIP FUNCTION

In fuzzy logic, to present the variables in linguistic terms, we use membership functions. In practice, membership functions can have several different types, such as [10]: triangular, trapezoidal, gaussian, two-sided gaussian, bell-shaped, sigmoid-right, sigmoid-left, and polynomial-Z. The exact type depends on the actual applications. In this paper, we focus much more on the triangular fuzzy number function since this type is close to human reasoning.

4.1. Fuzzy triangular number

The rating of criteria, weights and alternatives are represented in linguistic values such as: very low, low, medium, high, and very high. To manage the imprecision of such an assessment, we use fuzzy logic and more precisely triangular fuzzy sets. The use of this presentation is justified by the fact that the translation of human expertise to this type of fuzzy number is easier.

A triangular fuzzy number \tilde{N} is defined by a triplet (l, m, u) and the membership function $\mu_{\tilde{N}}(x)$ is defined by is defined as [17]:

$$\tilde{N} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x < a \\ \frac{x-a}{b-a} & \text{if } a \leq x \leq b \\ \frac{c-x}{c-b} & \text{if } b \leq x \leq c \\ 0 & \text{if } x > c. \end{cases}$$

Where a, b, c are real numbers and $(a < b < c)$.

A fuzzy triangular membership function has the following form Figure 1:

Figure 1. Fuzzy triangular membership function

5. FUZZY TOPSIS METHOD

The technique called fuzzy TOPSIS can be used to assess multiple alternatives against multiple conflicting criteria. The TOPSIS technique is an MCDM method that was initially proposed by [18], [19] subsequently introduced a fuzzy TOPSIS. Fuzzy TOPSIS is used when we want to solve an MCDM problem whose criteria and alternatives are evaluated with linguistic values. The optimal solution in classical TOPSIS

approach is close to the fuzzy positive ideal solution (FPIS) and extreme from the fuzzy negative ideal solution (FNIS) [20], [21].

Using fuzzy TOPSIS gives a profit to evaluate human opinion which consist of distinguishes between the interest (the better) and the cost (the less is the better) category criteria then chose the solutions close to the positive ones and far from the negative ones [4]. The previous version of TOPSIS stand on numerical values for both criteria weights and the alternatives. This presentation lead to ambiguity of understanding the human opinions which are vague and cannot be evaluated with exact numbers. To resolve the mention problem in TOPSIS, the experts combine it with fuzzy which is a set of MCDM approaches [22]. Fuzzy TOPSIS method has shown its powers in several areas and almost present in the majority of real world applications. Fuzzy TOPSIS is used in many real life applications [23]: energy, health, performance evaluation, personal selection, networks, health care, construction, business, manufacturing, and stock exchange.

6. PROPOSED APPROACH

The proposed approach is described is being as: before applying fuzzy TOPSIS method to choose the best web site E-commerce, it is important to follow the following steps; Form a committee of experts: we assume that we are a group of k experts (E_1, E_2, \dots, E_k) with m possible E-commerce websites which are evaluated against n criteria (C_1, C_2, \dots, C_n). These experts can be decision-makers just as they can be experts in the field of E-commerce. Identification of linguistic terms to assess criteria and websites E-commerce by the experts. Linguistic evaluation of E-commerce websites by customers. Application the fuzzy TOPSIS method. Final ranking. The following Figure 2 shows the detail of our proposed approach:

Figure 2. Proposed approach

6.1. Identification criteria

This step makes it possible to identify the set of criteria to be used to evaluate the SWEs. This task is principal. it is attributed to the experts since they are the ones who know the field of E-commerce. For this, it is important to choose the most influential criteria on the ranking of E-commerce websites.

6.2. Attribution of linguistic terms

This task is developed by the experts, it makes it possible, on the one hand, to identify the possible linguistic values for the quality of service criteria. These values will help the experts to assign weights for each

criteria. On the other hand, to identify the possible linguistic values that can be used by consumers to evaluate E-commerce websites according to each criterion.

6.3. Evaluation of E-commerce websites

This step allows consumers to evaluate E-commerce websites. Each consumer evaluates each site according to all the criteria initially defined by the experts.

6.4. Fuzzy technique for order preference by similarity to the ideal solution for E-commerce websites ranking

The fuzzy TOPSIS method is mainly based on the work of Chen [24], the steps of fuzzy TOPSIS as presented as shown in, [25]-[27]:

- Step 1: construct the decision matrix

We suppose that we have a group of k experts and n E-commerce websites which are evaluated according to the criteria $c_j (j=1,2,\dots,3)$. The evaluation of expert k th for the E-commerce website A_i according to the criterion C_j is noted:

$$\tilde{X}_{ij}^k = (a_{ij}^k, b_{ij}^k, c_{ij}^k).$$

The weights of the criterion is C_j is noted. $\tilde{W}_{ij}^k = (w_{j1}^k, w_{j2}^k, w_{j3}^k)$. The aggregated fuzzy values x_{ij} of the E-commerce websites for each criterion are given by: $X_{ij} = (a_{ij}, b_{ij}, c_{ij})$ where $a_{ij} = \min_k \{a_{ij}^k\}$, $b_{ij} = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{k=1}^k b_{ij}^k$ and $c_{ij} = \max_k c_{ij}^k$. The aggregated fuzzy weights w_{ij} for each criterion is calculated by:

$$w_{ij} = \min_k \{w_{j1}^k\}, w_{j2} = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{k=1}^k w_{j1}^k \text{ and } w_{j3} = \max_k w_{j1}^k$$

- Step 2: construct the normalized matrix

The normalized fuzzy matrix \tilde{R} is given by:

$$\text{For positive criteria: } \tilde{r}_{ij} = \left(\frac{a_{ij}}{c_j^*}, \frac{b_{ij}}{c_j^*}, \frac{c_{ij}}{c_j^*} \right) \text{ and } c_j^* = \max_i \{c_{ij}\}$$

$$\text{For negative criteria criteria: } \tilde{r}_{ij} = \left(\frac{a_j^-}{c_{ij}}, \frac{a_j^-}{c_{ij}}, \frac{a_j^-}{c_{ij}} \right) \text{ and } c_j^* = \min_i \{a_{ij}\}$$

- Step 3: construct the weighted normalized matrix

The weighted normalized matrix is given by:

$$\tilde{V} = [\tilde{v}_{ij}]_{m \times n} \text{ where } \tilde{v}_{ij} = \tilde{r}_{ij} \cdot w_{ij}$$

- Step 4: calculate the fuzzy ideal and fuzzy negative ideal solution

$$\text{The FPIS is calculated by: } A^* = (\tilde{v}_1^*, \tilde{v}_2^*, \tilde{v}_3^*) \text{ where } \tilde{v}_j^* = \max_i \{v_{ij3}\}$$

$$\text{The FNIS is calculated by: } A^- = (\tilde{v}_1^-, \tilde{v}_2^-, \tilde{v}_3^-) \text{ where } \tilde{v}_j^* = \min_i \{v_{ij1}\}$$

- Step 5: calculate the fuzzy distance for each E-commerce website

$$d_i^* = \sum_{j=1}^n d(\tilde{v}_{ij}, \tilde{v}_j^*) \text{ where } i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, m$$

$$d_i^- = \sum_{j=1}^n d(\tilde{v}_{ij}, \tilde{v}_j^-) \text{ where } i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, m$$

- Step 6: calculate the relative closeness to the ideal solution

This coefficient represents the distance of the positive ideal solution A^* and the negative ideal solution A^- :

$$CC_i = \frac{d_i^*}{d_i^- + d_i^*}$$

- Step 7: rank the alternatives

7. NUMERICAL ILLUSTRATION

To demonstrate the feasibility of our approach, we provide an illustrative example. The example is described in Table 1, we have four imaginary E-commerce websites: wse1, wse2, wse3, and wse4. These E-commerce websites are evaluated according to ten criteria (c1 to c10) whose the criteria from c1 to c8 are positive criteria, while the two criteria c9 and c10 are negative criteria. This operation passes with several steps: (i) linguistic term for criteria ratings : According to the different experts, each criterion can take one of the linguistic values presented in Table 1, the linguistic terms and the triangular fuzzy numbers are values are taken from the work [28]; (ii) linguistic assessment of criteria : each expert gives the importance of each criterion. The aim of this step is to calculate the weight of each criterion Table 2; (iii) criteria weights: the weight of each criterion is given by Table 3; (iv) linguistic assessment of the E-commerce websites: each customer (cus) assesses with a linguistic value each E-commerce website according to all the criteria. We obtain the linguistic assessment of the E-commerce websites Table 4; (v) in this step the previous table (see Table 5) presents the Aggregate Fuzzy matrix which explains the translation of calculated values from previous Tables; (vi) next step normalized fuzzy matrix, we give a meaning to each value by defining an interval for each criterion (Table 6); (vii) then we pass directly to step 7 which will calculate the weighted normalized matrix given in Table 7; (viii) the ideal positive fuzzy solution and the ideal negative fuzzy negative solution are illustrated in Table 8. After preparing the above mentioned tables, we pass directly to the last stages which consists of the fuzzy distance for each E-commerce website. The final step shows the closeness coefficient to classify the web site according to their respective distance.

Table 1. Linguistic term for criteria ratings

Linguistic term	Triangular fuzzy number
Very low (VL)	(1,1,3)
Low (L)	(1,3,5)
Medium (M)	(3,5,7)
High (H)	(5,7,9)
Very high (VH)	(7,9,9)

Table 2. Linguistic assessment of criteria

Criteria	Expert			
	E1		E1	
C ₁	H	C ₁	H	
C ₂	VL	C ₂	VL	
C ₃	H	C ₃	H	
C ₄	VH	C ₄	VH	
C ₅	VL	C ₅	VL	
C ₆	VH	C ₆	VH	
C ₇	VH	C ₇	VH	
C ₈	L	C ₈	L	
C ₉	VL	C ₉	VL	
C ₁₀	M	C ₁₀	M	

Table 3. Criteria weights

Criteria	Fuzzy weight
C ₁	(5,7,0000,9)
C ₂	(1,4,3333,9)
C ₃	(1,6,3333,9)
C ₄	(5,8,3333,9)
C ₅	(1,3,6667,9)
C ₆	(1,6,3333,9)
C ₇	(1,5,6667,9)
C ₈	(1,5,6667,9)
C ₉	(1,5,0000,9)
C ₁₀	(1,4,3333,9)

Table 4. E-commerce websites linguistic assessment

Criteria	wse ₁				wse ₂				wse ₃				wse ₄			
	Cus ₁	Cus ₂	Cus ₃	Cus ₄	Cus ₁	Cus ₂	Cus ₃	Cus ₄	Cus ₁	Cus ₂	Cus ₃	Cus ₄	Cus ₁	Cus ₂	Cus ₃	Cus ₄
C ₁	P	F	P	VP	C ₁	P	F	P	VP	C ₁	P	F	C ₁	P	F	
C ₂	VG	VG	G	VG	C ₂	VG	VG	G	VG	C ₂	VG	VG	C ₂	VG	VG	
C ₃	F	G	VG	VP	C ₃	F	G	VG	VP	C ₃	F	G	C ₃	F	G	
C ₄	VP	VG	VG	G	C ₄	VP	VG	VG	G	C ₄	VP	VG	C ₄	VP	VG	
C ₅	VG	G	VG	P	C ₅	VG	G	VG	P	C ₅	VG	G	C ₅	VG	G	
C ₆	P	VP	F	G	C ₆	P	VP	F	G	C ₆	P	VP	C ₆	P	VP	

Table 5. Fuzzy matrix

	<i>wse₁</i>	<i>wse₂</i>	<i>wse₃</i>	<i>wse₄</i>
<i>C₁</i>	(1, 3.66667, 7)	(1,5,9)	(5, 8.3333,9)	(1, 6.3333,9)
<i>C₂</i>	(5, 8.33333,9)	(1, 5.6667,9)	(1, 1.6667,5)	(1,3,5)
<i>C₃</i>	(3,7,9)	(1,2.3333,5)	(1, 4.3333,9)	(1,7,9)
<i>C₄</i>	(1,7,9)	(1, 4.33333,9)	(3,7,9)	(1,1,3)
<i>C₅</i>	(5, 8.33333,9)	(1,5,9)	(1,1,3)	(1, 6.3333,9)
<i>C₆</i>	(1,3,7)	(1, 4.33333,9)	(3, 6.3333,9)	(1,3,7)
<i>C₇</i>	(1, 4.33333,9)	(1, 6.3333,9)	(1, 5.6667,9)	(1,5,9)
<i>C₈</i>	(1,3,9)	(1,8.3333,9)	(1,5,9)	(1,5,9)
<i>C₉</i>	(1, 6.33333,9)	(1, 4.33333,9)	(1, 3.6667,7)	(1, 6.3333,9)
<i>C₁₀</i>	(7,9,9)	(1, 5.6667,9)	(1, 5.6667,9)	(1, 3.6667,9)

Table 6. Normalized fuzzy matrix

	<i>wse₁</i>	<i>wse₂</i>	<i>wse₃</i>	<i>wse₄</i>
<i>C₁</i>	(0.111,0.407,0.778)	(0.111,0.556,1)	(0.556, 0.1926,1)	(0.111,0.704,1)
<i>C₂</i>	(0.556, 0.926,1)	(0.111,0.630,1)	(0.111, 0.1185, 0.556)	(0.111,0.333,0.556)
<i>C₃</i>	(0.333, 0.778,1)	(0.111,0.259,0.556)	(0.111, 0.481,1)	(0.333,0.778,1)
<i>C₄</i>	(0.333, 0.778,1)	(0.111,0.481,1)	(0.333, 0.778,1)	(0.111,0.111,0.333)
<i>C₅</i>	(0.556, 0.926,1)	(0.111,0.556,1)	(0.111, 0.111, 0.333)	(0.111,0.407,1)
<i>C₆</i>	(0.111, 0.333,0.778)	(0.111,0.481,1)	(0.333, 0.704,1)	(0.111,0.333,0.778)
<i>C₇</i>	(0.111, 0.481,1)	(0.111,0.704,1)	(0.111, 0.630,1)	(0.111,0.556,1)
<i>C₈</i>	(0.111, 0.333,1)	(0.556,0.926,1)	(0.111, 0.556,1)	(0.111,0.556,1)
<i>C₉</i>	(0.111, 0.158,0.333)	(0.111,0.231,1)	(0.143, 0.273,1)	(0.111,0.158,1)
<i>C₁₀</i>	0.111,0.111,0.143	(0.111,0.176,1)	(0.111, 0.176,1)	(0.111,0.273,1)

Table 7. Weighted normalized fuzzy matrix

	<i>wse₁</i>	<i>wse₂</i>	<i>wse₃</i>	<i>wse₄</i>
<i>C₁</i>	(0.556, 4.926,7)	(0.556, 3.889,9)	(2.778, 6.481,9)	(0.556, 4.926,9)
<i>C₂</i>	(0.556, 4.012,9)	(0.111, 2.728,9)	(0.111, 0.802,5)	(0.111, 1.444,5)
<i>C₃</i>	(0.333, 4.926,9)	(0.111, 1.642,9)	(0.111, 3.049,9)	(0.333, 4.926,9)
<i>C₄</i>	(0.556, 6.481,9)	(0.556, 4.012,9)	(1.667, 6.481,9)	(0.556, 0.926,3)
<i>C₅</i>	(0.556, 6.481,9)	(0.111, 2.037,9)	(0.111, 0.407,3)	(0.111, 1.494,9)
<i>C₆</i>	(0.111, 2.111,7)	(0.111, 3.049,9)	(0.333, 4.457,9)	(0.111, 2.111,7)
<i>C₇</i>	(0.111, 2.728,9)	(0.111, 3.988,9)	(0.111, 3.568,9)	(0.111, 3.148,9)
<i>C₈</i>	(0.111, 1.889,9)	(0.556,5.247,9)	(0.111, 3.148,9)	(0.111, 3.148,9)
<i>C₉</i>	(0.111, 0.789,3)	(0.111, 1.154,9)	(0.143, 1.364,9)	(0.111, 0.789,9)
<i>C₁₀</i>	(0.111, 0.481,1.286)	(0.111, 0.765,9)	(0.111, 0.765,9)	(0.111, 1.182,9)

Table 8. Fuzzy positive ideal solution and fuzzy negative ideal solution

<i>A[*]</i>	9.000	9.000	9.000	9.000	9.000	9.000	9.000	9.000	9.000
<i>A⁻</i>	0.556	0.111	0.111	0.556	0.111	0.111	0.111	0.111	0.111

7.1. Fuzzy distance for each E-commerce website

After preparing the above mentioned tables we pass directly to the last stages which consists of the fuzzy distance for each E-commerce website is given by Table 9. In Table 10, the *wse2* E-commerce website is ranked as the best because it has the highest coefficient. The *wse3* E-commerce website is in the next rank. Finally the E-commerce website *wse1* and *wse4* are in the last positions. Analyzing the numerical illustration, we can conclude that fuzzy logic and more precisely the fuzzy TOPSIS method can be heavily used to rank E-commerce websites. Again, this approach can be broadened in application in several application areas.

7.2. Criteria weights with fuzzy analytical hierarchy process

Analytical hierarchy process (AHP) is a multi-criteria decision-making approach introduced by Saaty in 1980 [29]. It is characterized by its ability to manage different classes of qualitative and quantitative criteria. The fuzzy AHP technique is the extension of the traditional AHP method which supports linguistic data [30]. The MCDM method fuzzy AHP is widely used in the field of selection of alternatives sharing contradictory criteria. It also shows its power to assign weights to criteria. In this study we use fuzzy analytical hierarchy process (FAHP) to determine the weights of the criteria. Table 11 provides the weights of the qualitative criteria using the FAHP method [31].

Table 9. Fuzzy distance

	<i>wse</i> ₁	<i>wse</i> ₂	<i>wse</i> ₃	<i>wse</i> ₄		<i>wse</i> ₁	<i>wse</i> ₂	<i>wse</i> ₃	<i>wse</i> ₄
<i>C</i> ₁	3.9498	5.2415	6.0927	5.4897	<i>C</i> ₁	6,140	5,699	3,876	5,413
<i>C</i> ₂	5.6104	5.3498	2.8507	2.9257	<i>C</i> ₂	5,662	6,281	7,353	7,120
<i>C</i> ₃	5.8379	2.9577	5.4051	5.8379	<i>C</i> ₃	5,529	7,051	6,176	5,529
<i>C</i> ₄	5.9561	5.2681	5.9905	1.4274	<i>C</i> ₄	5,088	5,662	4,477	7,583
<i>C</i> ₅	5.477	5.2511	1.6767	5.1937	<i>C</i> ₅	5,852	6,519	7,934	6,717
<i>C</i> ₆	4.1415	5.4051	5.7139	4.1415	<i>C</i> ₆	6,595	6,176	5,650	6,595
<i>C</i> ₇	5.3498	5.5988	5.5064	5.4233	<i>C</i> ₇	6,281	5,892	6,014	6,144
<i>C</i> ₈	5.2336	5.9326	5.4233	5.4233	<i>C</i> ₈	6,572	5,335	6,144	6,144
<i>C</i> ₉	1.7133	5.1672	5.1827	5.1469	<i>C</i> ₉	7,798	6,845	6,752	6,986
<i>C</i> ₁₀	0.7111	5.1459	5.1459	5.1691	<i>C</i> ₁₀	8,388	6,996	6,996	6,835
\bar{d}_i	43.981	51.318	48.988	46.179	d_i^*	63,905	62,456	61,371	65,067

Table 10. Closeness coefficient with FuzzyTOPSIS

	wse1	wse2	wse3	wse4
\bar{d}_i	43,981	51,318	48,988	46,179
d_i^*	63,905	62,456	61,371	65,067
<i>CC</i> _{<i>i</i>}	0,408	0,451	0,444	0,415

Table 11. Criteria weights with FAHP

Criteria	Fuzzy weight
<i>C</i> ₁	(0.15 0.23 0.35)
<i>C</i> ₂	(0.13 0.23 0.36)
<i>C</i> ₃	(0.1 0.15 0.24)
<i>C</i> ₄	(0.04 0.06 0.1)
<i>C</i> ₅	(0.06 0.1 0.15)
<i>C</i> ₆	(0.05 0.09 0.14)
<i>C</i> ₇	(0.03 0.04 0.08)
<i>C</i> ₈	(0.03 0.04 0.08)
<i>C</i> ₉	(0.02 0.03 0.05)
<i>C</i> ₁₀	(0.01 0.02 0.03)

By applying the same algorithm with the same data only changing the weights of the criteria by applying the FAHP method. We obtain the following scores (Table 12): as we see in the previous table, the wse1 E-commerce website is ranked as the best because it has the highest coefficient. The wse2 E-commerce website is in the next rank. Finally, the E-commerce website wse3 and wse4 are in the last positions.

Table 12. Closeness coefficient with FAHP

	wse1	wse2	wse3	wse4
\bar{d}_i	0,850	0,851	0,776	0,766
d_i^*	0,993	1,072	1,062	1,092
<i>CC</i> _{<i>i</i>}	0,461	0,443	0,422	0,412

8. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

By analyzing Figure 3 which compares the two variants of scores: score with fuzzy TOPSIS whose weights are directly attributed by the experts and scores whose criteria weights are calculated through fuzzy AHP. We can quickly conclude that the scores assigned to the different E-commerce websites are not the same and this is due more precisely to the importance of the weights relative to the criteria in the ranking of the E-commerce websites.

Figure 3. Score comparison

9. CONCLUSION

In this study, we have presented a fuzzy logic based fuzzy TOPSIS algorithm for E-commerce websites ranking. The proposed approach is centered on the evaluation of consumers of E-commerce websites by linguistic values using fuzzy logic. The approach was illustrated with an example of E-commerce websites consisting of four E-commerce websites and ten criteria. The evaluation of E-commerce sites by consumers as well as the criteria and weights were presented in linguistic terms with the presentation of fuzzy triangular numbers. As the weights of the criteria play an essential role in the final result (scoring), we established a comparison of our proposal with data for which the weights of the criteria were calculated using the fuzzy AHP method. In the future and as work prospects, we will consider the following extensions: in order to improve the ranking process, we will introduce other quality of service measures; Develop another solution based on fuzzy inference engine and make a comparison with the current proposal; As the weights have a great influence on the ranking, we try to propose an MCDM method which performs the calculation of the weights of the criteria and then propose a hybrid solution of ranking.

REFERENCES

- [1] G. Yannis, A. Kopsacheili, A. Dragomanovits, and V. Petrakia, "State-of-the-art review on multi-criteria decision-making in the transport sector," *Journal of traffic and transportation engineering (English edition)*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 413-431, August 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.jtte.2020.05.005.
- [2] D. Dalalah, M. Hayajneh, and F. Batiha, "A fuzzy multi-criteria decision making model for supplier selection," *Expert systems with applications*, vol. 38, no. 7, pp. 8384-8391, July 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.eswa.2011.01.031.
- [3] S. F. Fam, J. Huang, Z. L. Chuan, S. N. Khalil, D. D. Prastyo, and F. N. M. Nusa, "Fuzzy TOPSIS method as a decision supporting system to rank Malaysia online shopping website quality during COVID-19 MCO 2020," *International Journal of Emerging Trends in Engineering Research*, vol. 8, no. 9, pp. 6397-6405, 2020.
- [4] A. Awasthi, S. S. Chauhan, and S. K. Goyal, "A fuzzy multicriteria approach for evaluating environmental performance of suppliers," *International journal of production economics* vol. 126, no. 2, pp. 370-378, Aug. 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.ijpe.2010.04.029.
- [5] R. Kumar, A. Baz, H. Alhakami, W. Alhakami, A. Agrawal, and R. A. Khan, "A hybrid fuzzy rule-based multi-criteria framework for sustainable-security assessment of web application," *Ain Shams Engineering Journal*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 2227-2240, June 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.asej.2021.01.003.
- [6] C. Bire, D. Kasse, and R. Bire, "Decision support system for selecting tourist attractions using fuzzy analytic hierarchy process," *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 1252-1261, June 2020, doi: 10.11591/eei.v10i3.3032.
- [7] K. Sahu, F. A. Alzahrani, R. K. Srivastava, and R. Kumar, "Hesitant fuzzy sets based symmetrical model of decision-making for estimating the durability of Web application," *Symmetry*, vol. 12, no. 11, p. 1770, 2020, doi: 10.3390/sym12111770.
- [8] C. R. Patnaik, S. N. Mohanty, S. Mohanty, J. M. Chatterjee, B. Jana, V. García-Día, "A fuzzy multi-criteria decision-making method for purchasing life insurance in India," *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 344-356, February 2021, doi: 10.11591/eei.v10i1.2275.
- [9] R. Kumar, A. I. Khan, Y. B. Abushark, M. M. Alam, A. Agrawal, and R. A. Khan, "An Integrated Approach of Fuzzy Logic, AHP and TOPSIS for Estimating Usable-Security of Web Applications," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 50944-50957, 2020, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2970245.
- [10] J. Zhao and B. K. Bose, "Evaluation of membership functions for fuzzy logic controlled induction motor drive," *IEEE 2002 28th Annual Conference of the Industrial Electronics Society. IECON 02*, vol. 1, pp. 229-234, 2002, doi: 10.1109/IECON.2002.1187512.
- [11] B. D. Rouyendegh, K. Topuz, A. Dag, and A. Oztekin, "An AHP-IFT integrated model for performance evaluation of E-commerce web sites," *Information Systems Frontiers*, vol. 21, no. 6, pp. 1345-1355, 2019, doi: 10.1007/s10796-018-9825-z.

- [12] S. Sulova, "A system for E-commerce website evaluation," *International Multidisciplinary Scientific GeoConference Surveying Geology and Mining Ecology Management, SGEM*, vol. 19, no. 2.1, pp. 25-32, 2019, doi: 10.5593/sgem2019/2.1/S07.004.
- [13] R. Van der Merwe and J. Bekker, "A framework and methodology for evaluating E-commerce web sites," *Internet Research*, 2003, doi: 10.1108/10662240310501612.
- [14] H. Zo and K. Ramamurthy, "Consumer Selection of E-Commerce Websites in a B2C Environment: A Discrete Decision Choice Model," in *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics-Part A: Systems and Humans*, vol. 39, no. 4, pp. 819-839, July 2009, doi: 10.1109/TSMCA.2009.2018633.
- [15] E. K. R. E. Huizingh, "The content and design of web sites: an empirical study," *Information and management*, vol. 37, no. 3, pp. 123-134, April 2000, doi: 10.1016/S0378-7206(99)00044-0.
- [16] R. Liang, J. Wang, and H. Zhang, "Evaluation of E-commerce websites: An integrated approach under a single-valued trapezoidal neutrosophic environment," *Knowledge-Based Systems* vol. 135, pp. 44-59, November 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.knsys.2017.08.002.
- [17] A. Kaufman and M. M. Gupta, "Introduction to fuzzy arithmetic," New York: Van Nostrand Reinhold Company, 1991.
- [18] Ching-Lai Hwang and K. Yoon, "Methods for multiple attribute decision making," *Multiple attribute decision making*, Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, 1981, pp. 58-191, doi: 10.1007/978-3-642-48318-9_3.
- [19] Shu-Jen Chen and Ching-Lai Hwang, Fuzzy multiple attribute decision making methods, Fuzzy multiple attribute decision making, 1992, pp. 289-486, doi: 10.1007/978-3-642-46768-4_5.
- [20] Ying-Ming Wang and T. M. S. Elhag, "Fuzzy TOPSIS method based on alpha level sets with an application to bridge risk assessment," *Expert systems with applications*, vol. 31, no. 2, pp. 309-319, August 2006, doi: 10.1016/j.eswa.2005.09.040.
- [21] N. B. Kore, K. Ravi, and S. B. Patil, "A simplified description of fuzzy TOPSIS method for multi criteria decision making," *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET)*, vol. 4, no. 5, pp. 2047-2050, 2017.
- [22] H. Han and S. Trimi, "A fuzzy TOPSIS method for performance evaluation of reverse logistics in social commerce platforms," *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 103, pp. 133-145, August 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.eswa.2018.03.003.
- [23] K. Palczewski and W. Sałabun, "The fuzzy TOPSIS applications in the last decade," *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 159, pp. 2294-2303, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.procs.2019.09.404.
- [24] Chen-Tung Chen, "Extensions of the TOPSIS for group decision-making under fuzzy environment," *Fuzzy sets and systems*, vol. 114, no. 1, pp. 1-9, August 2000, doi: 10.1016/S0165-0114(97)00377-1.
- [25] Chen-Tung Chen, Ching-Torng Lin, and Sue-Fn Huang, "A fuzzy approach for supplier evaluation and selection in supply chain management," *International Journal of Production Economics*, vol. 102, no. 2, pp. 289-301, August 2006, doi: 10.1016/j.ijpe.2005.03.009.
- [26] E. N. Madi, J. M. Garibaldi, and C. Wagner, "An exploration of issues and limitations in current methods of TOPSIS and fuzzy TOPSIS," *2016 IEEE International Conference on Fuzzy Systems (FUZZ-IEEE)*, 2016, pp. 2098-2105, doi: 10.1109/FUZZ-IEEE.2016.7737950.
- [27] P. Wang, K. Chao, C. Lo, C. Huang, and Y. Li, "A Fuzzy Model for Selection of QoS-Aware Web Services," *2006 IEEE International Conference on e-Business Engineering (ICEBE'06)*, 2006, pp. 585-593, doi: 10.1109/ICEBE.2006.3.
- [28] M. Hanine, O. Boutkhoum, A. Tikniouine, T. Agouti, "A new web-based framework development for fuzzy multi-criteria groupdecision-making," *SpringerPlus*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 1-18, 2016, doi:10.1186/s40064-016-2198-1.
- [29] R. W. Saaty, "The analytic hierarchy process—what it is and how it is used", *Mathematical modelling*, 1987, vol. 9, no 3-5, p. 161-176, doi: 10.1016/0270-0255(87)90473-8.
- [30] G. Kabir and M. A. A. Hasin, "Comparative analysis of AHP and fuzzy AHP models for multicriteria inventory classification," *International Journal of Fuzzy Logic Systems*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 1-16, October 2011.
- [31] I. Vinogradova, V. Podvezko, and E. K. Zavadskas, "The recalculation of the weights of criteria in MCDM methods using the bayes approach," *Symmetry*, vol. 10, no. 6, p. 205, June 2018, doi: 10.3390/sym10060205.

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